

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

A NEW POAG OPTIC NEUROPATHY TREATMENT, BASED IN THE UNSUSPECTED INTRINSIC PROPERTY OF EUKARYOTIC CELL TO DISSOCIATE THE WATER MOLECULE

Arturo Solís Herrera

MD, PhD.

María del Carmen Arias Esparza

MD, MsC.

Paola E. Solís Arias

MD, Ophthalmologist.

Sergey Suchkov

MD, PhD.

Human Photosynthesis™ Study Center, C. S. Aguascalientes 20000, México.

The Russian University of Medicine, Moscow, Russia.

Abstract

The POAG optic neuropathies result in optic disk damage and visual field loss. Ophthalmic medication therapy retards glaucoma progression, but many older patients require multiple medications to preserve vision and quality of life. Glaucoma is a leading cause of irreversible blindness, and early detection and treatment are crucial for preventing vision loss.

Conventional therapeutic techniques include eye drops and laser therapies, while emerging drug-eluting contact lenses can solve patient noncompliance with eye medications. Theragnostic platforms combine diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities into a single device. Advantages of these platforms include real-time monitoring and personalized medication dosing. By 2040, the number of people with glaucoma is expected to increase to 111.8 million, highlighting the urgent need for innovative diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

In this case report, we demonstrate the therapeutic results in a case of glaucoma, treated by pharmacological modulation of the unsuspected ability of the eukaryotic cell to dissociate the molecule from water, as in plants.

Keywords: Anterior chamber, Aqueous humor, Glaucoma, Iris, intraocular pressure.

Background

Glaucoma is the leading cause of irreversible blindness worldwide, affecting an estimated 3.5% of people aged from 40 to 80 years globally [1]. Most glaucoma cases go undetected and untreated, leading to irreversible vision loss and, ultimately, blindness.

Glaucoma is a chronic and slowly progressive disease of the optic nerve that tends to be asymptomatic in its early stages. When left untreated, or even in some treated cases, glaucoma can progress to irreversible tunnel vision or even complete visual field loss [2]. Elevated intraocular pressure (IOP) is considered a major risk factor for the development and progression of glaucoma.

Current diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for glaucoma have relevant limitations. As early-stage glaucoma is often asymptomatic, patients may experience delays in receiving diagnostic tests to detect glaucoma, thereby leading to delays in treatment.

Fluctuations and spikes in IOP are considered detrimental, like elevated average elevated IOP [3]. However, there is no practical method for measuring intraocular pressure fluctuations throughout the day, therefore, Goldman's applanation tonometry (GAT) is still considered the golden standard for the clinical measurement of intraocular pressure [4].

Continuous monitoring of IOP during daytime and sleep has been challenging in glaucoma care, especially due to the high incidence and prevalence of normal-tension glaucoma, which in some reports reaches 50%. This is attributed to technical problems related to the measurement of intraocular pressure and cases of poor adherence to treatment by the patient [5].

This is in relation to medical treatment, but we also face the problems inherent in surgical treatment [6], which, together, contribute to the fact that chronic open-angle glaucoma, high blood pressure and normal blood pressure glaucoma continue to be the leading cause of blindness, especially in sunny countries.

But the problem of glaucoma, both in diagnosis and treatment, stems from the fact that the excavation of the optic nerve, characteristic of glaucoma, is not mainly caused by the increase in intraocular pressure, but in this case report, we want to demonstrate that the ancestral problem of glaucoma, since the name comes from the Greeks; it's because the axons of the optic nerve tend to retract when oxygen levels inside the cells are below equilibrium levels that the eukaryotic cell requires [7].

Figure 1. The melanin contained in the iris, ciliary body, trabecular meshwork, etc., has the intrinsic property of dissociating and re-associating the water molecule.

The unfortunate and simplistic analogy between the exchange of gases within the lung at the level of the alveolar surface and the way in which a chimney works, proposed in the mid-eighteenth century, by intellectuals living in cold cities, where there were chimneys in abundance, has resulted in a significant setback in the advance of knowledge about the functioning from the biochemical point of view in relation to the human body. because to date it is a widely accepted dogma that the oxygen that our body requires for its proper functioning, comes from the atmosphere that surrounds it, when it cannot be so, because breathing is only to expel CO₂, and the air it introduces to the lungs only works to transport CO₂ to the outside, but never as a source of oxygen; because our body requires almost five times more oxygen than that found in the atmosphere (18 to 21 %), so we must correct this concept and implement a new biology and biochemistry that starts from the fact that the oxygen contained in our body comes from the interior of each cell that makes us up, based on the hitherto unknown ability of the eukaryotic cell to dissociate the molecule from water. just as it happens in plants [8].

The general biochemical reaction can be written as follows:

So, the main areas of production and reabsorption of aqueous humor are pigmented tissues, and not as much as we thought that aqueous humor is produced in the apex of ciliary processes of the ciliary body and then it was directed, through the pupil, from the posterior chamber to the anterior, ending in the trabecular meshwork and finally exiting through the aqueous veins.

Wherever melanin is found, the dissociation and re-formation of water molecules occurs, which implies

that we must re-think the biochemical logic not only of the retina, the retinal pigment epithelium, the iris, the choroid, etc., but of the entire organism. That is: pigmented tissues can produce water and dissociate it, so the same tissue that produces it (water) can reabsorb it by dissociating it, which would explain the formation and composition of aqueous humor and also of cerebrospinal fluid [9], among other examples.

Hence, current treatments, developed based on mistaken concepts, have not been able to modify an incidence and prevalence that has been sustained since the middle of the last century, and this throughout the world.

That is why we consider it important to report cases like this, which allows us to appreciate the great difference between both therapeutic approaches. That is: the traditional one, focused on lowering the intraocular pressure with topical drugs, laser therapy, and glaucoma surgery [10]; and the one developed by us, based on our observation about the hitherto unknown ability of melanin to dissociate and re-form water molecules.

Case Report:

A female patient, in the seventh decade of life, who comes with a history of having a valve placed in RE two years ago and cataract surgery with IOL placement, complying with infectious uveitis (RE). The cornea of the RE becomes opacified after valve surgery, also she has previous pterygium surgery in the eye (RE), several years ago. The opacification of the cornea of the right eye, was result of blood and purulent fluid that had accumulated in the anterior chamber of RE in the post operator (Figure 1, 2). At the initial examination, the SpO₂% was 92 %, and the PR-bpm was 68 per minute, measured by digital oxymeter.

Figure 1. The cornea in his right eye became opaque after Ahmed's valve surgery and intraocular lens insertion. Photograph taken on September 2017.

The edema of the cornea of the right eye presented mixed characteristics of a corneal ring abscess in the midperiphery, and signs of bullous keratopathy in the central region. Infectious endophthalmitis following intraocular surgery is a complication that could cause severe visual loss or loss of the eye. Most of the cases of postsurgical endophthalmitis are seen following cataract surgery [11].

The patient was operated on and treated for complications in another clinic, so we do not know the details of the treatment, but it is usually based on anti-inflammatories such as cortisone and strong broad-spectrum antibiotics, administered both locally and systemically.

During the first consultation, in the left eye, the intraocular pressure was 27 mm Hg, and the photograph of the left optic nerve is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Photograph of the left optic nerve of the patient, taken on November 3, 2017. It was particularly difficult to take the photograph due to the photophobia that the patient presented at the time of the examination.

The patient used, until that moment, Brimonidine tartrate, that is a highly selective alpha2-adrenergic receptor agonist indicated for the chronic treatment of glaucoma and ocular hypertension [12], ophthalmic drops presentation; every twelve hours in both eyes.

The patient and family members were explained the therapeutic approach that we use, as well as the differences with the glaucoma treatment that prevails so far, and once the respective informed consent was signed, we proceeded to suspend the medications she used, and we began with the pharmacological modulation of intracellular oxygen levels by QIAPI 1®. at the

dose of three sublingual drops every two hours, for the entire time the patient was awake.

Because the patient resided about 400 km from where we have our offices, communication was constant, via telephone, and the patient was able to attend a check-up until November 2020, and the photographs of that exam are shown below (Figures 3, 4, and 5.) During the November 2020 examination, the SpO2% was 96%, and PR bpm was 60 per minute, measured by digital oximetry.

Figure 3. Photograph of the right optic nerve of the patient, taken in November 2020, where we appreciated Ahmed's valve, located in the upper right region; and the corneal opacity with some increased because the patient had a corneal infection that was treated at her place of origin with topical antibiotics.

Figure 4. From the appearance of the scar, we assume that infectious episode, was due to a central corneal ulcer, which led to the greater opacity of the cornea. However, the cornea, at its periphery, remains transparent.

Figure 5. The photograph of the left optic nerve of the patient, shows a slight improvement in the retinal tissue, as some punctate hemorrhages have disappeared. The excavation of the optic nerve has not increased since 2017, and seems to have decreased slightly, compared to the first photograph (Figure 2).

Given the satisfactory evolution, the patient was instructed to maintain the same treatment and go for a check-up in twelve months. The photographs of the third consultation are shown below (Figures 6, 7, 8, and

9). The digital oximetry values during the consultation on October 1, 2022, were 98% in terms of SpO₂%, and 88 per minute in relation to PR bpm.

Figure 6. One year later, in October 2021, the appearance of the tissues of the anterior segment of the right eye are stable, the patient reports that she has no longer had episodes of inflammation, discharging, or tearing.

Figure 7. On examination with a biomicroscope, the cornea is thickened, apparently the anterior chamber is narrow. The periphery of the cornea is clear with some neo-forming vessels near the corneal surface.

Figure 8. The image of the anterior segment of the left eye does not show any pathology data, The photograph was taken in September 2021.

Figure 9. Left optic nerve, in September 2021. The appearance of the tissues of the retina, optic nerve, and choroid layer are quite satisfactory, after almost eight years of treatment with QIAPI 1©.

The patient was instructed to maintain the same treatment, and due to travel restrictions during the COVID 19 pandemic, she went to the clinic until March 22 of 2024, keeping in touch by telephone during the interval. The photographs taken during the March 2024

exam are shown below (Figures 10, 11, and 12). The digital oximetry values in March 2024 were 93%, in terms of SpO2%, and 65 per minute, in relation to PR bpm.

Figure 10., In October 2024, the appearance of the corneal surface seems more homogeneous, corneal neovascularization remains superficial.

Figure 11. Also in October 2024, the anatomical characteristics of the optic nerve are well preserved, and the excavation seems not to have increased and has even decreased slightly, which is compatible with adequate visual function, since the patient reports leading a normal life, without limitations.

Figure 12. The macular area of the left eye is of normal characteristics and appearance, its central vision is 20/20, and the visual fields are complete. The intraocular pressure of the left eye, it has remained around 18 mm Hg.

In 28 September 2024, the patient presented with moderate pain in OD, and the photographs of that day's

examination are shown in Figures 13, 14, and 15. Oximetry performed that day showed the following: SpO₂% of 93%, and 70 per minute of PR bpm.

Figure 13. Biomicroscopic examination of the right eye shows calcifications around the central area of the cornea. The cornea thickened, however the anterior chamber, narrow, but present.

Figure 14. The anterior segment of the left eye does not show significant alterations. Her intraocular pressure was 16 mm Hg, measured by Goldman applanation tonometry.

Figure 15. The excavation of the left optic disc shows no changes, the macular region remains in good condition. The discrete opacity is an artifact that appears with the 4 different wavelengths is since the pupillary dilation was mild at the time of the examination.

This case allows us to simultaneously evaluate the evolution of two problems: the evolution of the ring abscess after surgery of Ahmed valve implantation and intraocular lens placement, as well as the evolution of POAG optic neuropathy.

Corneal ring abscess has been described as a post-operative complication caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* presence and occurs not only after intraocular procedures instead after cardiac surgery [13]. Histological examination studies demonstrated that the ring abscess was a dense accumulation and aggregation of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMN) with debris of cells and lamellae in the deep stroma at the corneal margins, suggesting prevention of PMN migration to the central lesion [14].

Ring infiltrates usually accompany numerous infectious and sterile ocular disorders. Nevertheless, systemic conditions, drugs toxicity and contact lens wear may present with corneal ring infiltrate in substantial part with a significant its detrimental effect on vision [15].

On the other hand, the preservation of the anatomy and function of the optic nerve of the left eye is surprising, because after almost 8 years of follow-up with photographic controls, the visual function of the left eye within normal limits.

Conclusion

The current pathophysiological bases of glaucoma have not allowed the development of effective treatments that displace the high incidence and prevalence of this disease since the beginning of the last century. Surgical treatments, apart from complications such as the one reported here, are also no guarantee of being able to preserve useful vision.

The discovery of the unsuspected ability of the eukaryotic cell to transform the power of light energy into chemical energy, by means of the dissociation of water molecules, will allow us, at last; to overcome the gap in which biology, medicine, and ophthalmology find themselves in their struggle to overcome epidemiologically important diseases.

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Conflict of interest: The reported drugs were developed in our study center.

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